

Phase selective growth of $\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$ and Cu_3SbS_4 thin films by chalcogenization of simultaneous sputtered metal precursors

A. Shongalova^{a,c}, M. R. Correia^{a,b}, A. F. da Cunha^{a,b}, J. P. Teixeira^{a,b}, J. P. Leitão^{a,b}, J.M.V. Cunha^{a,f}, P.M.P. Salomé^{a,f}, P. A. Fernandes^{b,e,f,*}

^aDpto de Física, Universidade de Aveiro, Campus Universitário de Santiago, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

^bIN, Universidade de Aveiro, Campus Universitário de Santiago, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

^cSatbayev University, Satpayev street, 22a, 050013 Almaty City, Kazakhstan

^dIMEC, Kapeldreef 75, 3001 Leuven, Belgium.

^eCIETI / Dpto de Física, Instituto Superior de Engenharia do Porto, Instituto Politécnico do Porto, Rua Dr. António Bernardino de Almeida, 431, 4200-072 Porto, Portugal

^fINL - International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory, Av. Mestre José Veiga 4715-330 Braga Portugal

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2019.05.149>

Abstract

In this work, it is presented a procedure to grow single phase $\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$ and Cu_3SbS_4 thin films consisting on the annealing of simultaneously sputtered metal precursors flowed by a annealing treatment in a sulphur atmosphere. The selection of the ternary phase which is intended to grow is performed by adjusting the sulfur evaporation temperature in chalcogenization process. It is shown that for a sulphur evaporation temperature of 140 °C the predominant phase is $\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$ and for 180 °C the predominant phase is Cu_3SbS_4 . In order to ensure precursor composition homogeneity, the Cu-Sb metallic precursors are deposited simultaneously by rf magnetron sputtering using adjustable segmented targets. The morphological characterization of the films was made by scanning electron microscopy and the composition was analysed by energy dispersive spectroscopy. The structural analysis and phase identification were performed by X-ray diffraction and Raman scattering. The optical properties were studied through spectrophotometry on films deposited directly on bare glass.

Keywords: sulfosalt, thin films, RF magnetron sputtering, chalcogenization

1. Introduction

The photovoltaic market is dominated by technology based on Si, with a consistent price reduction of the systems over the past few years. The energy costs in high quality Si production are still an obstacle to a further drop in production costs. Thin film solar cells (TFSC) have been identified as an alternative to overcome this problem, supported by less use of materials, growth methods involving lower energy consumption, cheaper and more automation processes. Among the various materials tested for this technology, $\text{Cu}(\text{In,Ga})(\text{S,Se})_2$ (CIGS) and CdTe stand out for their high light to power conversion efficiency. However, these materials exhibit a significant intrinsic problem. In and Ga elements are scarce, and Cd is toxic. The scientific community has been studying materials that can replace CIGS and CdTe. Compounds like kesterites or perovskites have been intensively studied for this kind of applications. However intrinsic problems, such as the difficulty of growing high quality materials or device performance stability, can complicate their commercial implementation on a large scale.

$\text{Cu}_x\text{Sb}_y\text{S}_z$ compounds, generally designated as Sb-based sulfosalts [1], have shown optical absorptions higher than 10^5

cm^{-1} and optical bandgap energies between 1.1 to 2.5 eV, inside the energy range imposed by the Shockley–Queisser limit. These studies also revealed that their electronic properties, such as charge carriers density and mobility are compatible with semiconductor materials for TFSC applications [1–6]. In nature, the most common crystalline phases of this sulfosalt class are: CuSbS_2 (chalcostibite), Cu_3SbS_3 (skinnerite), Cu_3SbS_4 (famatinite) and $\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$ (tetrahedrite). This work is focused in the growth and characterization of the last two phases. A wide variety of atmospheric pressure based synthesis methods have been reported for the growth of Cu_3SbS_4 and $\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$. Chemical bath deposition, solvothermal and hydrothermal routes, hydrazine based chemical routes have been used to grow thin films and nanoparticles [5–9, 9–13]. Franzer *et al.* [14] presented a method to grow Cu_3SbS_4 thin film based on post annealing of magnetron sputtering precursors.

In this work, we propose a method of growing Cu_3SbS_4 and $\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$ thin films based on the deposition of Cu-Sb metallic precursors by RF-magnetron sputtering followed by an annealing step in a sulphur vapour atmosphere. The phase to be grown can be selected according to amount of sulphur supplied to the sample during the growth process. This amount can be tuned by changing the maximum sulphur evaporation temperature. The structural, compositional and structural characterization of the samples are presented as well as the optical analysis.

*Corresponding author.

Email addresses: jenniferpassos@ua.pt (J. P. Teixeira), joaquim.leitao@ua.pt (J. P. Leitão), pafernandes@ua.pt (P. A. Fernandes)

48 2. Experimental Methods

49 2.1. Sample preparation

50 This work shows a method to grow Cu-Sb-S based sulfosalt
51 thin film using sulphurization of simultaneous RF-magnetron
52 sputtered metal precursors. This process is formed by two
53 stages. The first stage refers to the deposition of the metallic
54 precursor layer, Cu and Sb, by RF magnetron sputtering. The
55 chalcogen incorporation, S, and the annealing process, which
56 allow for the crystalline phase formation, are performed in the
57 second stage.

58 The sample preparation process begins with a 3×3 cm² soda
59 lime glass (SLG) substrate cleaning, with successive ultrasound
60 baths of acetone/alcohol/deionised water. This step ends with
61 substrate being dried with a N₂ flow. Next, the precursor layer
62 is deposited directly in the SLG. This step is performed using
63 an Ar atmosphere at an operating pressure of 2×10^{-3} mbar. The
64 target is composed by a Sb base with a thickness of 1/8 inches
65 and 1 mm thick Cu segments placed over it as shown in Figure
66 1. The radial geometry of the segments ensures a uniform dis-
67 tribution of metals in the sample. Both base and segments have
68 a 4N purity. In order to adjust the composition of the metallic
69 precursors, the segments were produced with a limited area.
70 The thermal contact between the base and segments is assured
71 only by the mechanical grip using the metal ring of the sput-
72 tering gun. To avoid contamination no thermal paste is used.
73 The power density was 0.87 W/cm² for deposition of the metal
74 precursors.

Figure 1: The target setup used for the deposition of the metal precursors.

75 The 2nd stage was performed in a tubular furnace in a N₂ +¹¹³
76 sulphur vapour atmosphere at a constant working pressure close
77 to 500 mbar and a N₂ flow rate of 40 ml min⁻¹. Sulfur pellets,¹¹⁴
78 with purity 5N were evaporated using in a temperature con-
79 trolled quartz tube source. Two different sulphur evaporation¹¹⁵
80 temperatures are presented, 140 °C and 180 °C. The furnace¹¹⁶
81 temperature profile has 3 stages: first a temperature increase of¹¹⁷
82 10 °C min⁻¹, followed by a 5 min isothermal line at 480 °C and¹¹⁸
83 finally a natural cooling step to room temperature. The sulfur¹¹⁹
84 evaporator follows the same heating profile as the furnace and¹²⁰

85 remains at the maximum temperature until the temperature of
86 the furnace to cool down to 200 °C. At this point the evaporator
87 is switched off. These profiles are presented in figure 2.

Figure 2: Annealing and sulphur evaporator temperature profiles used for sulphurization process (2nd stage).

88 2.2. Sample characterization

89 The cross-sectional morphology and average composition of
90 the samples were analysed by scanning electron microscopy
91 (SEM) with a Hitachi Su-70 scanning electron microscope
92 equipped with a Rontec energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS)
93 system operated at an acceleration voltage of 4.0 kV for im-
94 age acquisition and 25 kV for chemical analysis. The crys-
95 talline structure was analysed by X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) with
96 a Philips PW 3710 system, in the Bragg-Brentano configura-
97 tion (θ - 2θ), using the Cu-K α line (wavelength $\lambda=1.54060$ Å)
98 and the generator settings were 50 mA and 40 kV. A LabRam
99 Horiba, HR800 UV spectrometer, equipped with a solid state
100 laser (excitation wavelength, $\lambda_{exc}=532$ nm) was used for the Ra-
101 man scattering measurements. Absorbance measurements were
102 done using a Shimadzu UV3600 spectrophotometer equipped
103 with an integrating sphere. The photoluminescence (PL) mea-
104 surements were performed with a Bruker IFS 66v Fourier trans-
105 form infrared (FTIR) spectrometer, equipped with a Ge diode
106 detector. The samples were placed in a He gas flow cryostat.
107 The 514.5 nm line of an Ar⁺ ion laser was used as the excita-
108 tion source. The excitation power was measured at the front of
109 the cryostat window. The correction of the spectral response of
110 the Ge detector was performed for all spectra.

111 The sample naming scheme uses the sulphur element symbol
112 S followed by the maximum temperature of the sulphur evapo-
rator.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Compositional characterization

The main objective of this work is the growth of thin
films of ternary compounds of Cu-Sb-S, namely Cu₃SbS₄ and
Cu₁₂Sb₄S₁₃ and to evaluate the influence of sulfur concentra-
tion in its growth. In the course of this study several anneal-
ing/sulphurisation temperatures were tested. However, in order

121 to keep the presentation simple only the most relevant results,¹⁵⁹
 122 corresponding to the sulphurization temperature of 480 °C and¹⁶⁰
 123 to sulphur evaporation temperatures, of 140 °C and 180 °C, are
 124 shown. With these thermodynamic conditions, Sb_2S_3 evapo-
 125 ration losses are minimized, allowing the growth of only one
 126 predominant ternary crystalline phase. In addition, with these
 127 processing conditions, a better phase crystallinity is obtained
 128 compared with the ones grown at lower temperatures (not pre-
 129 sented).

130 The adjustment of the metal precursors' composition is made
 131 by placing more or less Cu segments on the Sb target base. This
 132 procedure changes the area exposed to the plasma of each ele-
 133 ment, changing the amount of sputtered metal from the target
 134 and consequently arriving at the sample. An exhaustive study
 135 is made of the precursors composition behavior with the area
 136 of the metal target. The results of this study are shown in figure
 137 3 where metal composition ratios are plotted against the ratios
 138 of the areas. In figure 3 a), the metal composition ratio,
 139 $[Cu]/[Sb]$, is plotted against the exposed area ratio, A_{Cu}/A_{Sb} ,
 140 with a polynomial fitting used as a guide to the eye. These
 141 results show a regular behaviour between these two param-
 142 eters, with the Cu compositions increasing significantly for area
 143 ratios from 2.25 to 3.5. The figure 3 b) shows the composi-
 144 tion variation obtained from different deposition runs with the
 145 same area ratios. These variations are explained by metal target
 146 interdiffusion during the deposition process. Nevertheless this
 147 behaviour is predictable and can be minimized by replacing the
 148 Cu segments on the Sb base, as shown in the figure for differ-
 149 ent deposition runs. In Figure 3 b), the data set represented by
 150 open circles and crosses show the results for depositions under
 151 the same conditions after the replacement of the Cu segments.

Figure 3: a) Metal composition ratios versus the ratios of the areas of the target elements for different composition tests. b) Composition variations for the same target areas from different deposition runs. Different symbols mean a different set of Cu segments.

152 The Figure 4 shows a ternary diagram with the composition
 153 of the sulphurized samples. Samples that were sulphurized us-
 154 ing a sulphur evaporation temperature of 140 °C, samples S140,
 155 are closed to stoichiometric $Cu_{12}Sb_4S_{13}$ phase. On the other
 156 hand, higher S availability during the annealing process, ob-
 157 tained in the growth of the S180 samples, show composition re-
 158 sults closer to stoichiometric Cu_3SbS_4 phase. In this work, no

sample approached compositions close to the two other com-
 pounds belonging to the same family, $CuSbS_2$ and Cu_3SbS_3 .

Figure 4: Composition ternary diagram of the studied samples. This graphs also show the known Cu-Sb-S ternary compounds with stoichiometric compositions.

3.2. Morphological and structural characterization

3.2.1. Morphological characterization

161 Surface morphology was studied using SEM imaging. Figure
 162 5 shows the results of this analysis for samples S140 and S180.
 163 Both samples show rough surfaces with a uniform distribu-
 164 tion of aggregates. Sample S180 presents bigger grains than
 165 S140. Despite these properties, no cracks or voids were ob-
 166 served. Changes in the sulphurization temperature profile must
 167 be done in order to lower the film surface roughness.
 168
 169

Figure 5: Top surface SEM micrographs of S140 (on the left) and S180 (on the right) samples.

170 3.2.2. XRD characterization

171 Figure 6 shows the results of XRD measurements for the
 172 samples with a sulphur evaporation temperature of 140 °C. The
 173 assignment of the crystalline phases was done using the Inter-
 174 national Centre for Diffraction Data (ICDD) database [15]. Ac-
 175 cording to this database, several phases can be assigned, but the
 176 best matches are Cu_3SbS_3 with a cubic structure I-43m (Space
 177 group 217), datasheet reference code number 01-075-1574,
 178 and $\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$ with a cubic structure I-43m (Space group
 179 217), commonly known as tetrahedrite, datasheet reference
 180 code number 04-017-1329. Using the information provided by
 181 composition analysis done by EDS, section 3.1, and the results
 182 obtained by Raman scattering characterization, shown in sec-
 183 tion 3.2.3, we concluded that the prominent crystalline phase
 184 in these samples are tetrahedrite. It is interesting to note that
 185 these two datasheets report the same XRD reflections and cell
 186 parameters for different chemical species, which is very un-
 187 likely. Further studies should be performed in order to clar-
 188 ify this point. From this diffraction pattern, it can be seen that
 189 the peaks are sharp which indicate that the samples have good
 190 crystalline quality. The diffractograms also present the highest
 191 counts for the peak located at a diffraction angle, 2θ , 29.94° ,
 192 corresponding to the (222) planes.

Figure 6: XRD diffractograms of the sample with a sulphur evaporation temperature of 140 °C. The phase assignment was done using the ICDD database [15].

193 Figure 7 presents the diffractogram for the sample with a sul-
 194 phur evaporation temperature of 180 °C. In this graph, the peak
 195 position for several crystalline phases is also presented, but in
 196 this case a clear matching is obtained. Higher sulphur content
 197 environment promote the growth of Cu_3SbS_4 with a tetragonal
 198 structure I-42m (Space group 121), datasheet reference code
 199 number 04-006-8349, commonly named as famatinite. These
 200 results show sharp peaks indicating a good crystalline prop-
 201 erties. The most intense reflection is located a 2θ close to 28.7° ,
 202 corresponding to the (112) planes.

203 3.2.3. Raman scattering characterization

204 Next, the Raman scattering results are presented. Figure
 205 8 shows on top the Raman results of tetrahedrite mineral ex-
 206 tracted from RUFF database, reference RRUFFID: R100204
 207 and the fitted peaks. These peaks were adjusted with Lorentzian[217

Figure 7: XRD diffractograms of the samples with a sulphur evaporation temperature of 180 °C. The phase assignment was done using the ICDD database [15].

functions using a multiplex fitting technique. The Raman scat-
 212 tering measurements of the sample S140 are presented in Fig-
 213 ure 8 below. Comparing these two graphs, we can observe a
 214 concordance in the location and shape of the spectra. This al-
 215 lows to conclude that S140 is mainly formed by tetrahedrite. As
 216 shown in this figure, the main Raman modes are located at 323,
 346 and 356 cm^{-1} . The findings are in agreement with Rath *et al.* [7]. Unreported modes are also visible for lower frequency shifts, 53, 66, 78 and 102 cm^{-1} .

Figure 8: Top: Raman spectrum and the peak fitting results of tetrahedrite mineral extracted from RUFF database, reference RRUFFID: R100204. Below: Raman spectrum and the peak fitting results of sample S140.

For samples annealed with a sulphur evaporation temperature

of 180 °C, the Raman scattering results are presented in Figure 9. On top, the Raman results of famatinite mineral extracted from RUFF database, reference RRUFFID: R110022 with fitted peaks. The fitting procedure follows the same method as previously referred. The Raman scattering measurements of sample S180 are shown in Figure 9 below for a frequency shift ranging from 200 cm⁻¹ to 400 cm⁻¹. The results are similar, indicating that the sample is constituted mainly by Cu₃SbS₄. The main Raman modes for this crystalline phase are located at 244, 273, 317 and 344 cm⁻¹ [8, 9]. Previously unassigned peaks can be observed at lower frequency shifts 58, 71, 90, 133, 143, 190 cm⁻¹. The peak sharpness, especially 273, 317, 344 cm⁻¹, indicate good crystalline properties.

Figure 9: Top: Raman spectrum and the peak fitting results of famatinite mineral extracted from RUFF database, reference RRUFFID: R110022. Below: Raman spectrum and the peak fitting results of sample S180.

3.3. Absorbance characterization

The results of the absorbance measurements are shown in Figure 10 a) and b) for sample S140 and S180, respectively. The measurements were performed for radiation in the visible and near IR regions, between 400 nm and 1600 nm. The S140 results show a absorbance threshold close to 700 nm.

Based on the absorbance results, *Abs*, and the thickness of the films, the absorption coefficient, α , can be extracted using the following expression:

$$\alpha = 2.303/d \times \log(I_0/I) = 2.303/d \times Abs \quad (1)$$

where I_0 and I are the incident and transmitted intensity, respectively, and d is the path length/film thickness. The average

film thickness, measured by step profilometer were 1.38 μm and 1.73 μm , for S140 and S180, respectively. The resulting absorption coefficient is shown in Figure 10 c) and d), for samples S140 and S180, respectively. In both cases, the studied materials are compatible with thin film solar cells technology, presenting absorption coefficient values higher than 10^3 cm^{-1} .

Figure 10: a) Absorbance measurement results for sample S180 plotted against the radiation wavelength from 400 nm to 1600 nm. b) Absorbance measurement results for sample S140 plotted against the radiation wavelength from 400 nm to 1600 nm. c) and d) Optical absorption coefficients for S180 and S140, respectively, against the photon energy.

The relation between the absorption coefficient and the nature of the optical transition can be defined by the following expression [16, 17]:

$$(\alpha h\nu)^m = A(h\nu - E_g) \quad (2)$$

where A is a constant, m defines the nature of the transition, $h\nu$ is the photon energy and E_g is the band gap energy. The value of the power m is 1/2 (allowed) or 1/3 (forbidden) for indirect transitions and 2 (allowed) or 2/3 (forbidden) for direct transitions. To estimate which types of transitions generate the absorption edges shown in figure 10 c) and d), the values of $(\alpha h\nu)^m$ were plotted against the photon energy. From the powers values mentioned previously, the best results were obtained for $m = 2$, which means that the nature of the transition was direct allowed. As presented in Figure 11, extrapolating the results of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ to zero the band gap energies point to values close to a) 1.57 eV for S140 and close to b) 0.89 eV for S180. These values are in good agreement with previously reported values for the tetrahedrite and famatinite phase, respectively [6–8, 10].

Figure 11: Tauc plots of the samples a) S140 and b) S180, showing the estimated energies values for direct transitions. The inset tables show the linear fitting parameters used for the bandgaps estimation.

3.4. Photoluminescence characterization

The PL spectra at low temperature, for both samples, are shown in Figure 12. For S140 no luminescence was measured in the entire detection range of the Ge detector. We ascribe this result to the existence of non-radiative recombination channels that capture free charge carriers, enabling their radiative recombination. In the case of S180, a broad and asymmetric band is observed from 0.76 to 0.89 eV. This energy range is compatible with the estimated bandgap value, 0.89 eV (see Figure 10). Thus, we ascribe the luminescence to radiative recombination channels in the Cu_3SbS_4 crystalline phase. The high full width at half maximum of the luminescence, suggest a large density of defects in accordance with PL results for other semiconductors [18–20]. Despite the low signal-to-noise ratio, the asymmetry of this band suggest the presence of two components. However, more PL measurements are required to clarify this issue.

4. Conclusion

In this work we describe a method to grow selectively $\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{14}$ and Cu_3SbS_4 thin film by changing the sulphur supply during the sulphurization/annealing process. By controlling the sulphur evaporation temperature, different crystalline phases are obtained. We also tested simultaneous metal sputtering using single target which allows the precursors, Cu and Sb, compositions adjustments. The crystalline phase identification was performed using structural characterization using XRD and Raman scattering techniques. For a sulphur evaporation temperature of 140 °C the prominent crystalline phase is

Figure 12: PL spectra measured at 5 K for samples S140 and S180, with a 514 nm excitation wavelength.

tetrahedrite, $\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{14}$, with a cubic structure. For a sulphur evaporation of 180 °C the main phase is famatinite Cu_3SbS_4 with a tetragonal structure. Optical analysis allowed the estimation of the band gap energies. For the bandgap values were 1.57 eV and 0.89 eV for $\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{14}$ and Cu_3SbS_4 , respectively, both with direct allowed transitions.

5. Acknowledgements

This work was funded by FEDER funds through the COMPETE 2020 Programme and National Funds through Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) under the projects UID/CTM/50025/2013 and RECI/FIS-NAN/0183/2012 (FCOMP-01-0124-FEDER-027494). M. R. Correia thanks the facilities and technical support provided by CICECO- Aveiro Institute of Materials for the reflectance measurements. P. M. P. Salomé acknowledges FCT through the project IF/00133/2015. A. Shongalova acknowledges the funding of Erasmus + program 2016/17. J. M. V. Cunha acknowledges the funding of FCT through the project PD/BD/142780/2018.

References

- [1] M. Bouroushian, *Electrochemistry of metal chalcogenides*, Springer Science and Business, (2010).
- [2] C. Garza, S. Shaji, A. Arato, E. P. Tijerina, G. A. Castillo, T. D. Roy and B. Krishnan, *p-Type CuSbS_2 thin films by thermal diffusion of copper into Sb_2S_3* , *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, 95, 2001-2005, (2011).
- [3] B. Yang, L. Wang, J. Han, Y. Zhou, H. Song, S. Chen, J. Zhong, L. Lv, D. Niu and J. Tang, *CuSbS_2 as a promising earth-abundant photovoltaic absorber material: a combined theoretical and experimental study*. *Chem. Mater.*, 26 (10), pp 3135–3143, (2014).
- [4] C. Yan, Z. Su, E. Gu, T. Cao, J. Yang, J. Liu, F. Liu, Y. Lai, J. Lia and Y. Liua, *Solution-based synthesis of chalcostibite (CuSbS_2) nanobricks for solar energy conversion*, *RSC Advances*, 2, 10481-10484, (2012).
- [5] K. Ramasamy, H. Sims, W. H. Butler and A. Gupta, *Selective nanocrystal synthesis and calculated electronic structure of all four phases of copper-antimony-sulfide*, *Chemistry of Materials*, 26(9), 2891-2899, (2014).
- [6] J. van Embden, K. Latham, N.W. Duffy, Y. Tachibana, *Near-infrared absorbing $\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$ and Cu_3SbS_4 nanocrystals: synthesis, characterization, and photoelectrochemistry*, *J Am Chem Soc.* (2013), 7, 135 (31), 11562-71.

- 326 [7] T. Rath, A. J. MacLachlan, M. D. Brown and S. A. Haque, *Structural, optical and charge generation properties of chalcocite and tetrahedrite copper antimony sulfide thin films prepared from metal xanthates*, J. Mater. Chem. A, 2015, 3, 24155.
- 327
- 328 [8] U. Chalapati, B. Poornaprakash, Si-Hyun Park, *Growth and properties of Cu_3SbS_4 thin films prepared by a two-stage process for solar cell applications*, Ceram. Int. 43, 6, (2017), 5229-5235.
- 329
- 330 [9] K. Aup-Ngoen, T. Thongtem, S. Thongtem, *Characterization of Cu_3SbS_4 microflowers produced by a cyclic microwave radiation*, Mater. Lett., 66 (2012), 182-186.
- 331
- 332 [10] G. H. Albuquerque, K.-J. Kim, J. I. Lopez, A. Devaraj, S. Manandhar, Y.-S. Liu, J. Guo, C.-H. Chang and G. S. Herman, *Multimodal characterization of solution-processed Cu_3SbS_4 absorbers for thin film solar cells*, J. Mater. Chem. A, 2018,6, 8682-8692.
- 333
- 334 [11] B. John, G. G. Silvena, A. L. Rajesh, *Temperature dependent solvothermal synthesis of Cu-Sb-S nanoparticles with tunable structural and optical properties*, Materials Research Bulletin 95 (2017) 267-276
- 335
- 336 [12] L. Shi, C. Wu, J. Li, J. Ding, *Selective synthesis and photoelectric properties of Cu_3SbS_4 and $CuSbS_2$ nanocrystals*, Journal of Alloys and Compounds 694 (2017) 132-135
- 337
- 338 [13] L. Wang, B. Yang, Z. Xia, M. Leng, Y. Zhou, D.-J. Xue, J. Zhong, L. Gao, H. Song, J. Tang, *Synthesis and characterization of hydrazine solution processed $Cu_{12}Sb_4S_{13}$ film*, Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells, 144 (2016) 33-39
- 339
- 340 [14] N. D. Franzer, N. Paudel, C. Xiao, Y. Yan, *Study of RF sputtered Cu_3SbS_4 thin-film solar cells*, IEEE 40th Photovoltaic Specialists Conference (PVSC), 2014.
- 341
- 342 [15] cubic- Cu_3SbS_3 datasheet number: 01-075-1574; orthorhombic- Cu_3SbS_3 datasheet number: 04-009-6500; monoclinic- Cu_3SbS_3 datasheet number: 04-009-0846; tetragonal- Cu_3SbS_4 Farnatinitite datasheet number: 04-006-8349; cubic- $Cu_{12}Sb_4S_{13}$ datasheet number: 04-017-1329; International Centre for Diffraction Data technical report.
- 343
- 344 [16] J. Bardeen, F. J. Blatt and L. H. Hall, *Photoconductivity Conference*, Wiley, New York, 1956.
- 345
- 346 [17] R. A. Smith, *Semiconductors*, Cambridge University Press, London, 1959.
- 347
- 348 [18] J. P. Teixeira, R. A. Sousa, M. G. Sousa, A. F. da Cunha, P. A. Fernandes, P. M. P. Salomé and J. P. Leitão, *Radiative transitions in highly doped and compensated chalcopyrites and kesterites: The case of Cu_2ZnSnS_4* , Phys. Rev. B, vol. 90, p. 235202 (2014)
- 349
- 350 [19] P. M. P. Salomé, J. P. Teixeira, J. Keller, T. Torndahl, S. Sadewasser, and J. P. Leitão, *Influence of CdS and ZnSnO Buffer Layers on the Photoluminescence of $Cu(In,Ga)Se_2$ Thin Films*, IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics, vol. 7, 670 (2017)
- 351
- 352 [20] N. Ben Sedrine, R. Ribeiro-Andrade, A. Gustafsson, M. R. Soares, J. Bourgard, J. P. Teixeira, P. M. P. Salomé, M. R. Correia, M. V. B. Moreira, A. G. De Oliveira, J. C. González, and J. P. Leitão, *Fluctuating potential in GaAs:Si nanowires: critical reduction of the influence of polytypism on the electronic structure*, Nanoscale, vol. 10, p. 3697 (2018)
- 353
- 354
- 355
- 356
- 357
- 358
- 359
- 360
- 361
- 362
- 363
- 364
- 365
- 366
- 367
- 368
- 369
- 370
- 371
- 372
- 373
- 374